

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: COLE****FIRST NAME: MARK****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7)
2. The phases of essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8-11)
3. Some rules of thumb (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12-14)
4. The English language (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25)
5. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, page no. 34)
6. CMS and the crib sheet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41-43)
7. Latin usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 59)

THE IMPORTANCE OF ESSAY WRITING

1) THE ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic writing, by its nature, requires a certain amount of uniformity and structure in order to facilitate scholarship and benefit the academic community. Academic essays – shorter, focused papers – are an important part of the infrastructure of scholarly writing. While essays are not exactly formulaic, there are similarities and guidelines that are detectable and recommended for writers of scholarly essays (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7).

2) THE PHASES OF ESSAY WRITING

There are some distinct phases of essay writing that every successful essayist will move within and through. Experienced authors know that these phases or stages are not exactly sequential, and sometimes one can blast through a phase quickly and sometimes not. Even so, there are certain phases or stages which are always present. I would call

these phases preliminary, drafting, and finalizing and further define them as follows (Cleenewerck and Gulma have more phases, but fundamentally, the flow and sequencing they suggest are the same as what I suggest).

Preliminary: Analyze your question, do credible research (read and take notes), organize your thoughts and tentative conclusions, and develop an essay plan (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7-9).

Drafting: Put pen to paper, take the first shot at the essay, set it aside, and continue mulling it over for a day or two (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021).

Finalizing: Edit, proofread, get third-party peer review, check citations, and complete the essay.

Again, these phases are rarely equal in duration or importance, and sometimes, they are not even strictly delineated. However, within this whole construct, the importance of research and references cannot be overstated. A key difference between scholarly, academic writing, and journalism is that the global community of scholars needs simple access to other scholars' sources to check and repurpose each other's scholarship and to further their own research and thinking. Accordingly, scholarly essays, like all forms of scholarly writing, need to be fully and consistently annotated (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 12).

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB

“Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper” Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 12 and 13) could be summarized as follows: state your conclusion early (do not bury your lead...), keep your essay focused and on track, keep assertions and argumentation clear, crisp and reasonable, your language active, precise and non-monotonous, participate in the scholarly discussion in good faith, citing used resources appropriately, doing your own analysis and drawing your own well-supported conclusions.

In short, academic papers, including essays, should be efficient, interesting, engaging, documented, original and thought-provoking. This is how the academic community advances scholarship.

4) THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

English is, of course, the dominant language on the planet Earth. Many people speak English as a first language, but many more use English as their professional language. As such, English occupies a global position not unlike Latin in Europe during the Roman Empire and the Christian Middle Ages: a transnational, functional, and official language. But even scholars who use English as their professional language have another choice to make: American or British English.

And that choice matters. Once made, an author using American English should stick to American conventional spelling, punctuation, meaning, syntax, and terminology. Mixing American and British English in an academic essay should not happen.

5) PLAGIARISM

The point of originality is worth making again. Plagiarism is something academics take seriously, and we must do so. Plagiarism is not only professionally unethical, it strikes at the heart of what we do, which is advancing thought, research, analysis, scholarship, collaboration, and debate.

Plagiarism drastically undermines trust and creates suspicion – precisely the opposite of scholarly values. Scholarship, by its nature, depends on rigorously documented original thought, the honest transmission of knowledge, and absolute integrity. Plagiarism erodes the foundation of scholarship itself, just as theft erodes private property and free cooperation and creates an environment of suspicion and fear.

The antidote to plagiarism is proper annotation. When in doubt, cite your sources.

6) CMS AND THE CRIB SHEET

The use of uniform formatting, style, and presentation in academic papers is critical to the scholarly vocation. A style guide such as the Chicago Manual of Style promotes the values of efficiency, transparency, clarity, and collaboration. Imagine the orchestral music world if every country or orchestra used different notation. Or the world of transport if every railroad or region used a different gauge of rail trackage. In such a world exchange, commerce, collaboration, and development become impossible. And so, it is when scholars use the Chicago Manual of Style. The entire scholarly enterprise benefits from the judicious use of a style guide.

The CMS crib sheet is a helpful, condensed summary tool and shorthand reference guide that will help writers easily access some of the main points of the CMS. It is particularly useful in noting the differences between the notes-bibliography and author-date styles. The crib sheet also underscores the comprehensive guide for book publishing and sets forth guidelines on everything from capitalization and quotation treatments to the complexities of referencing a wide array of sources. Taken all together, the crib sheet (and the CMS) supports the scholarly enterprise by maintaining rigorous, uniform, transparent standards in writing and research documentation – something that we tend to take for granted. But imagine again, what would our world be like if every author used their own form of style and citation?

7) LATIN USAGE

For better or for worse, Latin terms and abbreviations have worked their way into English scholarly writing. Given that reality, uniformity of usage is again essential. More than fifty Latin terms are listed and defined (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, pages no. 59-64). Some of them are more obscure than others. While it is undeniable that using Latin abbreviations gives a scholarly writer some *prima facie* credibility (see what I did there?), I tend to think that clarity, simplicity, and robust English should be preferred at all times. Why use Latin when English will do? That said, when using Latin, it is important that uniform standards be applied so that we are all speaking the same language. Again, this facilitates the scholarly enterprise.

8) CONCLUSION

In this response, I have touched upon the stages of scholarly essay writing: initial research, drafting, and finalization. These stages, when completed, should ensure rigor and coherence for an essay. The vital role of accurate referencing has been highlighted. Proper annotation will always be a necessary component of academia and for the facilitation of dialogue among scholars.

I have also noted the near global ubiquity of the English language and that choosing between the two major variants (English and American) is important for internationally minded scholars.

The ethical violation of plagiarism has been noted, and the reliance of academia on a foundation of trust and demonstrable originality has been noted. I have championed the use of the Chicago Manual of Style as a tool of uniformity and noted that the CMS crib sheet – a distillation of the entire manual – is noted as a useful shortcut for navigating citation and formatting conventions.

To conclude, understanding essay construction, English language variations, integrity and originality, and the significance of style guides is necessary for academic success. These basic components are the backbone of scholarly writing, and scholarly writing is the backbone of the academic exchange of knowledge.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.